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JOB STRESS AND CAREER PROGRESSION OF WOMEN

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Abstract: Stress and tension experienced by women in the workplace is a crucial issue. It is a problem that both men and women face, but the impact on both is different. The role of women is crucial in the three areas of family formation, development and survival. Male-dominated jobs and workplaces often create barriers to women's employment and career advancement. It is often impossible for women to take part in power struggles in male-dominated workplaces. Organisations turn down women from certain jobs, roles and positions because they consider such jobs, roles and positions as masculine. A drastic change in the mindset of the organisations is highly essential for ensuring equal importance and opportunities for both men and women.

Keywords: Job, Job stress, women, career advancement, female CEOs

Introduction

Unexplained fatigue and depression is a common occurrence among women working in various fields. Some women tell their partner this problem while others tell it to their friends. But some people put up with it without telling anyone. But rarely do they recognize this silent killer who is attacking them. That killer is none other than the stress he has to face in his job. It is like the savior assuming the role of a murderer. A job that is accepted to protect oneself and one's family silently kills and eliminates a person. But the annoying fact is that neither the person nor his family members can understand this.

What is Stress?

A person has to face many different situations in his daily life. But the everyday, normal, and familiar situations do not make a significant difference in his mental and physical condition. But some unexpected and unusual situations can affect a person either positively or negatively. It may cause some changes in his mental and physical condition. Anger, sadness, fear, anxiety, happiness, affection, and love all arise from the interactions with situations that a person has to face in his life. State of life of a person changes according to the nature, significance, severity, and fluctuations of the circumstances. For example, the loss of ten rupees is not the same as the loss of ten thousand rupees.

Some children find it harder to be reprimanded by their father than their mother. In short, the impact of a situation on an individual can lead to a variety of stressors. “I never thought this would be such a big headache”. There is no one who does not say such a sentence at least once. What is actually referred to as a headache is the stress that the person is experiencing. Circumstances require many things from one person or a person may have to do many things to cope with an extraordinary situation. This responsibility puts pressure on the person.

One Life and Many Situations

Life is one, but circumstances are not the same. It keeps changing. Their nature is also different. Some may be positive for a person while others may be negative for him. When a favorable situation makes a person feel safe and healthy, an unfavorable situation creates mental and physical discomfort in him. Survival is about being able to adapt to changing circumstances and move on with life. But overcoming the stress caused by such changes is extremely difficult. This is because of the gap between a person's survival skills and the challenges she/he face. An individual is able to withstand the pressures of the situation to some extent through improved survival capacity.

What, Why and How of Job Stress

Job or occupation is considered to be the livelihood of an individual. In addition to meeting basic needs such as food, clothing and shelter, job also helps an individual to achieve other goals. Among them major goal is social and economic progress. occupation must evolve in such a way as to enable a person to have good personal relationships, economic growth, a healthy mind and body, and a joyful family life. Otherwise the person will be denied the fundamental right to a quality life. The nature of the work, the working conditions, and the nature of the individual are the main factors determining the dynamics of work stress.

A job is very different from other jobs in terms of work structure, physical and mental work, work style and other characteristics. The stress and strain experienced in each of these jobs is unique. For example, repetitive work can make a person bored. The work environment plays an important role in determining work stress. Prolonged work hours, overwork, unsafe workplace, poor personal relationships and workplace discrimination are all factors that increase work stress. Personal characteristics increase or decrease work stress. When one of the two co-workers feels stressed, the other does not have to or both may experience different levels of stress.

Job Stress in Women

Stress and tension experienced by women in the workplace is a crucial issue. It is a problem that both men and women face, but the impact on both is different. It has been mentioned in many studies. Physical differences between men and women, psychological differences, and differences in social context have all been cited as reasons for this. Such differences also affect the process of managing the stress of women and men. The family is considered as the cornerstone of any society. The role of women is crucial in the three areas of family formation, development and survival. In most societies, the management of the family has been reserved for women since ancient times. Male participation in domestic work is very low. Women play an important role in child rearing, their education, cooking and parental care. Perhaps it is difficult to complete household chores efficiently in the absence of women. In this perspective, women have to perform two tasks simultaneously. One is the maintenance of the family and the other is the official responsibilities. This increases the psychological stress of women compared to men. Male-dominated jobs and workplaces often create barriers to women's employment and career advancement.

Women do not get the representation they deserve in many governing bodies and in strategic positions of various organisations. Women are under-represented in key positions, despite their skills, abilities, knowledge, and intelligence, as well as their higher qualifications and experience. Visual and invisible gender discrimination increases women's work stress and tension. In many institutions, women's career advancement and promotions are being stifled by invisible glass ceilings. This is gender discrimination that cannot be quickly identified. Apparently gender equity and equality are the basic tenets of many organisations and in practice, they take contradictory measures. Although women may be represented at the primary levels of such institutions, women are indirectly denied opportunities in higher positions.

Are Women Moving Back or Being Pushed Back?

Women are either left behind or pushed back when they are unable to cope with the pressure of intense competition to reap the benefits. Women often try to reduce formal congestion and problems by taking into account the difficulties that may arise in domestic matters. This engenders many obstacles to their achievements in the official sphere. It is often impossible for women to take part in power struggles in male-dominated workplaces. It is a daunting task for women to get the adequate support from corners. Women are reluctant to hold high positions in such situations. Those who go ahead by ignoring the crisis are left behind in many situations.

Women Heads of State or Government

There are only 16 women serving as heads of state or Government among the 195 countries in the world. This is only 8% of the total number of heads of state in the world. The table below shows the details of the women heads of state in the world. Sirimavo Bandaranaike of Sri Lanka was the first democratically elected female Prime Minister, taking over the leadership of the Sri Lanka Freedom Party when her husband was slain in 1959. Angela Merkel of Germany (16 years, 16 days), Dame Eugenia Charles of Dominica (14 years, 328 days), and Ellen Johnson Sirleaf of Liberia (12 years, 6 days) are the women heads of states who have held offices for the longest periods of time. Indira Gandhi (16 years, 15 days) and Sheikh Hasina of Bangladesh (over 18 years in total) held the records for the longest combined non-consecutive mandates. Only 76 women in the world have occupied the most prominent executive positions in their respective countries since 1960.

List of Women Heads of State in the World

Sl.No.	Country	Name	Position
1.	New Zealand	Jacinda Ardern	Prime Minister
2.	Tunisia	Najla Bouden	Prime Minister
3.	Serbia	Ana Brnabić	Prime Minister
4.	Slovakia	Zuzana Čaputová	President
5.	Denmark	Mette Frederiksen	Prime Minister
6.	Moldova	Natalia Gavrilița	Prime Minister
7.	Bangladesh	Sheikh Hasina	Prime Minister
8.	Estonia	Kaja Kallas	Prime Minister
9.	Namibia	Saara Kuugongelwa	Prime Minister
10.	Finland	Sanna Marin	Prime Minister
11.	Greece	Katerina Sakellaropoulou	President
12.	Moldova	Maia Sandu	President
13.	Georgia	Salome Zourabichvili	President
14.	Ethiopia	Sahle-Work Zewde	President
15.	Trinidad and Tobago	Paula-Mae Weekes	President
16.	Lithuania	Ingrida Šimonytė	Prime Minister

Female CEOs in the Corporate World

Female senior executives make up only 8% of the global CEOs. Thailand has the greatest percentage of female CEOs in the world, with 30% of enterprises hiring female CEOs, followed by the People's Republic of China (19%). The proportion of female CEOs in the European Union is 9%, while in the United States it is 5%. (Asiaone Business, 2011). In India, the number of female CEOs has declined over the past six years, according to Deloitte's recent report on Women CEOs worldwide. According to a Deloitte survey report in 2016, the percentage of women in executives in India fell from 6.6% in 2016 to 3.4% in 2018 and 4.7% in 2021, well below the previous level. According to Fortune Magazine, the Fortune 100 companies in India had only five female CEOs in 2020-21, Soma Mondal, director of SAIL. Anamica Roy Rashtrawar, IFFCO Director, Padmaja Chundurur, MD, Indian Bank; Vinita Gupta, CEO, Lupin and Zarin Daruwala, CEO Standard Chartered Bank India. However, it is interesting to note that Soma Mondal and Zarin Daruwala were appointed as the first female CEOs in their company's history. In the words of Seema Bangia, VP & chief people officer, Mahindra Agri, Defence and Aerostructure, "a mindset has been created leading people believe that women are incapable of taking up certain positions at the corporate level."

Why Women are Sidelined?

In the political, social and all other fields of life, the general belief of the society is that men are natural leaders who possess essential qualities of leadership but women with the same qualities are penalized for appearing unfeminine. Women go through a different socialization process than men. Even in childhood, men tend to be more motivated to lead, compete, and take risks than women. As a result, men have more opportunities to develop these skills, which will help them to advance and succeed in lead roles in the society. Organisations whether social, political or economical are reluctant to elevate women to top positions. Work-family balance is a crucial issue that limits women's search for leadership roles in different organisations.

Conclusion

Notwithstanding several blocks and barriers in the career advancement of women, organisational culture and mindset is the most important obstacle. Organisations turn down women from certain jobs, roles and positions because they consider such jobs, roles and positions as masculine. A drastic change in the mindset of the organisations is highly essential for ensuring equal importance and opportunities for both men and women. Organizations must ensure that their career ladders have sufficient set of steps to allow women to reach leadership positions.

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